

PRESENTATION OF SILVOPASTURE SYSTEMS

[Pre-orchards, Hedgerows, etc.]

1. Charolais bull in a pasture with trees and hedgerows - Hoeffel Walbourg Farm ©Ver de Terre Production 2. Lacaune ewes in a forested plot 3. Shropshire sheep grazing in an apple orchard at Christophe Bitauld's farm. 4. Black Janzé chickens in the apple orchards of Christophe Bitauld.

THE WHAT AND WHY

Silvopasture is the integration of wooded areas and livestock on the same land. The livestock can include sheep, cattle, goats, or pigs, and poultry farming can also be incorporated into this practice with poultry pasture under forests or fruit trees.

This system serves both forestry and pastoral goals that work in synergy. The introduction of trees or hedgerows in pastures improves animal welfare, soil decontamination, and the protection of groundwater, enhances carbon balance, maintains wooded spaces, provides diverse woody forages, and diversifies agricultural production. The management of grass cover and fertilization of the plots are controlled through the rotation of livestock between different paddocks.

HOW THE CHALLENGE IS ADDRESSED

The choice of plot management and livestock type depends on pedoclimatic conditions, available animal and plant species, and production goals.

For example, pre-orchard systems, particularly common in Normandy, allow farmers to combine fruit trees and grazing to optimize the profitability of their operations. However, these systems are not without challenges. The presence of animals during harvest can be problematic: their manure can contaminate the fruit, and the fruit may be crushed or consumed. To avoid these issues, farmers must remove the animals from the plots before harvest. To minimize prolonged land idleness, a solution is to group different tree varieties within the same plot, allowing for better management of grazing and harvest periods.

Another example is poultry management in agroforestry. Rotating pastures is essential for regenerating vegetation and maintaining good animal health. This relies on alternating between several zones, allowing each plot to have adequate rest time. Ideally, a rest period of about two months between rotations is recommended, if possible. In the case of a fixed building, installing trapdoors on several sides helps facilitate access to different plots, which can then be alternated, optimizing space management.

When a pasture is intended to host crops or cover vegetation, such as maize or grasses, adapted management is necessary. Plowing or seeding these plots often requires a longer rest period. This downtime may extend to an entire year, allowing crops to fully develop before the animals can graze again. This organization ensures better sustainability of the pastures while maintaining their productivity.

Keywords: Pre-orchards, Poultry agroforestry, Agroforestry grazing, Silvopasture, Agroforestry poultry

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ADVANTAGES

Pre-orchard systems leverage the complementarity between fruit trees and livestock to offer several benefits. For instance, the presence of animals helps maintain the pasture, preparing it for fruit harvest. This reduces fuel use for mechanical mowing and decreases nitrogen fertilizer needs through the livestock's manure. Moreover, these extensive systems lower orchard maintenance costs, even though fruit production is generally lower compared to intensive orchards. The trees also provide shade, enhancing animal comfort during hot weather, thus promoting their welfare. Additionally, a single plot can be used for multiple simultaneous productions, such as fruit, milk, meat, and even honey. In some regions, trees play a key role in regulating grass production by delaying pasture drying during dry periods, sometimes up to four weeks.

Another example is poultry management in agroforestry. Trees offer shade and protection against predators while boosting biodiversity. The design includes hedgerows and thickets to guide the poultry and stabilize the soil, while specific plants provide nutritional or medicinal properties. These pastures support nutrient cycling, attract beneficial wildlife, and ensure better manure distribution, thus reducing pollution. Animal welfare is enhanced by reduced heat stress, lower parasitic risks, and the prevention of undesirable behaviors like pecking. Poultry express their natural behaviors, increasing productivity. Furthermore, these systems reduce feed costs and add value to poultry products raised in sustainable environments.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- **Agroforestry systems, such as pre-orchards, combine trees and livestock to optimize profitability, enhance animal welfare, and reduce maintenance and input costs.**
- **In poultry agroforestry, trees provide protection and well-being for poultry, promoting their productivity and reducing costs, while pasture rotation ensures soil regeneration and farm sustainability.**
- **Despite their advantages, these systems require careful management to avoid issues related to animal presence during harvest and to effectively organize grazing periods.**

Silvopasture: Suckler cows in a grazed agroforestry plot - EARL des Vieilles Rues
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CAMILLE ARCHAMBAUD

AND ASSOCIATION FOR AGROFORESTRY DYNAMICS IN NORMANDY (ADAN)

Ver de Terre Production

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